

ISSUES OF FORMATION AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC TERMS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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It is known that the role of the teaching and educational process in the formation of the younger generation is invaluable. In this process, textbooks and teaching aids in the native language play an important role. As early as the beginning of the 20th century, the Jadidists (from the Arabic word for "new") were the organizers of nine-meaning schools in Turkestan. Since at that time no native language textbooks had yet been created, the teachers used Tatar and Turkish grammars, which were based on Arabic terms.

For the first time the society "Chigatai gurungi" (Chagatai Talk) headed by A. Fitrat started the scientific study of the Uzbek language, which resulted in the appearance of new textbooks. Thus, two of Fitrat's textbooks were published in 1925. It should be noted that prior to the appearance of these textbooks, there were heated debates over the creation and use of linguistic terms. Some insisted on using traditional Arabo-Persian and Russian terms, while others insisted on Uzbek proper terms.

- on Uzbek proper terms. Elbek and Fitrat had a special place in the solution of this problem. In 1923, for example, Elbek published a work titled "Lugat va atamalar" in the journal Tur- kiston. This book recommended the use of proper Uzbek terms instead of Arabic: odot "ku'shimcha" (ending), modai asli "(stem), zamir-"olmosh" (pronunciation), etc.

Thus, as early as in 20-30s of the 20th century the foundation of the modern Uzbek linguistic terminology was laid.

Let's consider the old and modern grammatical terms of the Uzbek language in a sequence.

Since the phonetics was explained very briefly in the early textbooks, the phonetic terms appear in insignificant quantities. Thus, "vowel - purely tonal, voiced" in the works of Elbek and Fitrat is described by the term choozgli (choozmok "to stretch, to stretch"). Parallel to this term in Elbek's works are such terms as tovush-xarfi "the voice of the letter," tovushlik (tovush

"voice"). According to Sh. E. Babamuratova, at the same time, some linguists used the following terms to denote the notions of voiced and unvoiced consonants: tovushli - to-vushsiz, hurofe sit - hurofe samii, svuzich

- kiska, chuzyzyzy - chuzyzyzyzyzyzyzyz, suzyyk - tortiq. In 1926, Uzbek linguists coined the term unli, which is still in use today. In the past, the terms voiced and unvoiced consonant were also expressed by the terms tovushlik and unsi "without voice. A sound that differs from other sounds by a greater degree of gating, a decrease in the soundness and role assigned to the vocal pitch, and a smaller volume of exhaled air, subsequently became known as undos. This term is still used today.

The accent was denoted by the term bosim

"pressure." At this stage, the concept is fixed by the term urghu.

Let us turn to the past and present state of morphological terms. Since Elbek's linguistic heritage, including linguistic terms in his works, was considered in Sh. E. Babamuratova's PhD thesis, we investigated the formation of morphological terminology in Fitrat's works "Sarf" and "Naxv". It is well known that morphology studies

"...various aspects of the structure of a word in terms of the dependence of its meaning on its constituent morphemes" . That is why morphology has terms peculiar only to this branch of grammar. There are terms that are still in use today

in the textbook, "Sarf" (Morphology). These are: üshimchalar "endings," from "noun," üzak "root," tub söz "non derivative word," üshma from "compound noun," küplik "plural," birlik "singular." Suffat, now si-fat "adjective name", yasama sufat "derivative adjective", suz yasash "word-formation", kumakchi "postpositional", son "numeral name", fel "verb", and olmosh "pronoun".

At the same time, some terms from Fitrat's textbook were replaced in the modern Uzbek language by more adequate ones: sira son for tar-tib son "ordinal numeral", ulush son

- taksim sleep "separative numeral", sanalmishsiz sleep - sanok sleep "quantitative numeral", urtaklik sleep - jamlovchi sleep

Numerals", "numeration", "numeration", "numeral", "non-transitive word", "non-transitive word", "kumakchi souslar", "recollective words", "ashirma son", "chama son", and "indefinite numeral".

"indefinite numeral", belgilar

kelishiklar "cases" etc.

One of the sections of grammar, syntax, also has its own, peculiar terms in its arsenal. It is only natural that scholars such as Fitrat, Elbek, and others... should strive to create conditions for the development of the younger generation's oral and written language. To this end, in addition to the syntactic sections in the above-mentioned grammars, an attempt was made to create a separate textbook on the syntax of the Uzbek language. The syntactic terminology of the Uzbek language owes much to Fitrat's Syntax. First, it should be noted that this textbook uses terms that have survived to the present day: gap "sentence", kesim "predicate", ega "subject", aniklovchi "definition", kirish souz "introductory

The textbook also offers the following examples.

At the same time, this textbook contains terms that are not used at the present stage because syntactic concepts are now denoted by other terms. This is the first term to be used in the textbook, but it is not used at the present stage because syntactic

concepts are now denoted by other terms.

Thus, in many ways the modern linguistic terminology of the Uzbek language was formed in the above-mentioned early textbooks and tutorials by Fitra-t, Elbek, etc. However, a special role in the creation and unification of linguistic terms belongs to the textbooks created in 1938 and 1939, authored by Alim Usmanov and B. Avizov. Many of the terms used in these textbooks are still in use today. To clarify the state of the linguistic terms used in this textbook, let us look at examples from the corresponding sections of grammar.

Phonetic terms: phoneme (tovush), xarf (letter), unli (vowel), unli tovush (vowel sound), undosh (consonant), undosh tovush lar (consonant sounds), sonorlar, shovqinlilar (noisy), portlovchilar (explosive), bougin (syllable), purik bougin (open syllable), yopik bougin (closed syllable), sous urugusi (accent), logik urugu (logical accent), etc. п.

Morphological terms: uzak (root), prefix, birlik (singular), kuplik (plural), kelishik (case), bosh kelishik (nominative case), tushum ke-lishigi (accusative case), (dative, (directive) case), ūrin-pait kelishigi (local case,) chikish kelishigi (original case), sifatdosh (pronominal case), etc. п.

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